

A Comparative Study of Human Embryonic Organogenesis in Islam and Embryology

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: February 20, 2022</p> <p>Accepted: September 21, 2022</p> <p>Keywords : Organogenesis, Alaqah, Mudgha</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7097848</p>	<p><i>Man from time immemorial is in search of his origin and the process of his creation. Many explanations of man's creation can be seen in scientific (as evolution and embryology) and religious text. The paper aims to compare the Quranic text of man organogenesis inside her mother womb with the embryological studies of organogenesis. The focus will be on the ear, eye, muscles, bone formation and gonadal differentiation in comparison of the Quranic ayah and ahadith with the embryological studies to find either these embryological studies coincide with Quranic information.</i></p>

Introduction

Man, the crown of creation (the paragon of animals) is created by Allah almighty in best of the forms as Quran says

“لَقَدْ خَلَقْنَا الْإِنْسَانَ فِي أَحْسَن تَقْوِيمٍ”

“Verily, We created man in the best form.” (Quran 95: 4)

The above-mentioned verse of Quran elaborates that Almighty Allah created and fashioned man in most beautified manner by giving him the best form and shape. The process of creation of man inside the mother womb is a complicated process that can be explained in term of different stages, (fertilization, implantation, suspended mass, somites formation etc.) passing through which, the fetus gains the normal morphology as well as physiology of each organ. The stage that characterized the formation of normal morphology of human organs is called organogenesis through which the formation of organs of the embryo starts developing as the fetus and completed as a human baby. The time that marks this specific stage consists on third to eight weeks of development when the three germ layers ectoderm, endoderm and mesoderm give rise to specifically particular tissues and organs. The main organ system gets to establish and at the end of embryonic period it further leads to the development of external body features (Sadler, 2003).

The process of organogenesis from three germ layers is mentioned in the Holy Quran as

“يَخْلُقُكُمْ فِي بُطُونِ أُمَّهَاتِكُمْ خَلْقًا مِّنْ بَعْدِ خَلْقٍ فِي ظُلُمَاتٍ ثَلَاثٍ”

“He it is who creates you inside your mother womb, in stages, one after another, in three veils of darkness.” (Quran39:6)

The Arabic word *Khalaqa* (created) in three veils of darkness negates the traditional explanation of the verse. The traditional scholar was equating the three veils of darkness to three extra embryonic membranes as the placenta (with its chorine-amniotic membrane), uterinal wall and abdominal wall (Abadi, 1944). It is worth mentioning here that the verse of Quran emphasizes on “inside the mother womb” which refers to the uterus. Here it seems clear that the abdominal wall which lays outside the uterus and uterinal wall is the wall of uterus while on the other hand the amnion forms the amniotic sac filled with fluid that surround the embryo and fetus. The size of this amniotic cavity increases slowly as the fetus expels urine in the amniotic cavity in the beginning of 11th weeks. The outcome of this can be seen in increase of fluid at 10th week to 30ml, at 20th week to 350 ml and in 37th week it reaches to 1000ml (Persuade, 2003) The function of these three layers is protective while Quranic word “يَخْلُقُكُمْ” indicates the process of creation in three veils of darkness scientifically named as ectoderm, endoderm and mesoderm.

In this research paper the embryonic organogenesis of Islam and embryology will be compared in the context of eye, ear, bones, muscles formation as well as sex determination, especially at the level of gonadal differentiations.

Eye and Ear Formation

The Quran mentions that the faculties of hearing and seeing of human embryo simultaneously. In *Surah Al Dahar* Allah Almighty says

”إِنَّا خَلَقْنَا الْإِنْسَانَ مِنْ نُطْفَةٍ أَمْشَاجٍ نَبْتَلِيهِ فَجَعَلْنَاهُ سَمِيعًا بَصِيرًا“

“Verily We [sic] created man from a drop of mingled sperm, in order to try him: So, We gave him (the gifts) of hearing and sight.” (Quran76:2)

Thus, according to the Quranic explanation the sequence of human creation begins with fertilization (*mingled sperm*) (76: 2), the fertilized egg is then implanted in uterinal wall of mother. In Quranic verse it is mentioned as the embryo is place at rest firmly fixed. For a period (of gestation), determined

”أَلَمْ نَخْلُقْكُمْ مِنْ مَّاءٍ مَهِينٍ فَجَعَلْنَاهُ فِي قَرَارٍ مَكِينٍ إِلَىٰ قَدَرٍ مَعْلُومٍ“ (Quran 77: 20-22)

then changed in to suspended thing (*alaqah*) “ ثُمَّ خَلَقْنَا النُّطْفَةَ عَلَقَةً فَخَلَقْنَا الْعَلَقَةَ مُضْغَةً ” (Quran23: 14) after this it is differentiated into three germinal layers ectoderm, mesoderm, endoderm (three veils of darkness) 39:6, then somites formation called *mudgha* which is chewed like substance takes place.

As, Quran is book of signs, so Allah Almighty has explained this sign (as mentioned above) of different embryonic stages in the Quran, which now are comparable to recent embryological studies. The embryo till the stage of *Mudgha* (chewed like substance) which scientifically is called somites. Its formation is partly differentiated and partly remains undifferentiated.

Al-Quran reveals,

”ثُمَّ مِنْ مُضْغَةٍ مُخَلَّقَةٍ وَغَيْرِ مُخَلَّقَةٍ“

“Then out of chewed-like substance (*mudgha*) partly differentiating and partly un-differentiating.” (Quran22: 5)

Here the term differentiating referred to the process in which the eye, ear, bone and muscle formation occurs, while the un-differentiating denotes to the undifferentiating gonads of the embryo which means that till this stage the gonads are not differentiated into ovaries or testes.

This Quranic information is now supported with the recent studies that state that the developing eyes appear as a shallow groove on the side of the forebrain of embryo at the 22nd day of pregnancy. This neural tube closes with the passage of time and these grooves form out, as pocketing of the forebrain, optical vesicles (Sadler, 2003). The first indication of the eyes is optical groove that is formed in the beginning of fourth week of development (Persuade, 2003). While during the sixth week (42 days) from mesenchyme the eyelids develop (Persuade, 2003). Similarly, in the embryo of 22days the first indication of the ear results on each side of rhombencephalon as the thickening on the surface of ectoderm. These are named as optic placodes (Sadler, 2003). While the external ear of the embryo is formed by the development of the auricular hillocks during 5th week (stage 14) to 8th week (stage 23) (Hill).

Hearing - Outer Ear Development - Embryology (unsw.edu.au)

In a hadith Prophet Mohammad (P.B.U.H.) explains the process and the time of eyes formation in the following words,

“When forty nights pass after the semen gets into the womb, Allah sends the angel and gives him the shape. Then he creates his sense of hearing, sense of sight, his skin, his flesh, his bones, and then says: My Lord, would he be male or female? And your Lord decides as He desires and the angel then puts down that also and then says: My Lord, what about his age? And your Lord decides as He likes it and the angel puts it down. Then he says: My Lord, what about his livelihood? And then the Lord decides as He likes and the angel writes it down, and then the angel gets out with his scroll of destiny in his hand and nothing is added to it and nothing is subtracted from it.” (Muslim, 2009)

Bones and Muscles Formation

The process of differentiation after developing the faculty of hearing and seeing, leads further to bones and muscles formation. The Quran mentions the bones formation first and also gives detail such as the bones will be covered with the muscles with the degree of Almighty Allah.

”فَخَلَقْنَا الْمُضْغَةَ عِظَامًا فَكَسَوْنَا الْعِظَامَ لَحْمًا“

“We made out of lump the bones and clothed the bones with flesh. (Quran23: 14)

As in the hadith (mentioned above) the flesh and bone formation start after 40 days just as the embryonic study reveals that the limb bud appears at the end of the fourth week as an out pocket from the ventrolateral body wall (Sadler, 2003). The condensation of lateral mesoderm plate within the limb takes place in the fifth week (R.W. Dudek). The mesenchymal tissue in the hand plates condenses to form digital rays by the end of the sixth week. The mesenchymal tissue condensation further leads to outlining of the fingers. Similar condensation of mesenchymal tissue in the toe bud forms foot fingers in the seventh week. The mesenchyme is induced to develop in to mesenchymal primordial of the bones in the digits by a part of the apical ectodermal ridge at the tip of each digital ray . Thus, at the end of 6th week the entire limb skeleton is cartilaginous in nature and as time passes long bones forms. The aggregation of the myoblast will result in the formation of muscles in each limb bud, differentiated in to dorsal and ventral components. Finally the bones, ligaments and blood vessels in the limb buds forms from Mesenchyme (Persuade, 2003).

Gonadal differentiation

Gonadal differentiation is the stage in which the reproductive system of the human embryo differentiated into testis or ovaries. This gonadal differentiation is based on the chromosomal makeup of the embryo. If XX

chromosomes are present then the embryo has ovaries while in case of XY the embryo will be going to have testis. As these two ovaries and testis are very different in appearance and physiology but the same progenitor tissue are responsible for their development which are named as genital ridge and the primordial germ cells. These both tissues have potentiality to either differentiate into testes and ovaries (Jr., 2002). The intermediate mesoderm provides the rudiments of gonads (testes or ovaries) that appears during week 4th and remain undifferentiated (neither differentiated into testes or ovaries) until the 7th week (Gilbert, 2003). Again, the time of angel arrival coincides the period of 7th week. According to *hadith*

“The Prophet said, "Allah puts an angel in charge of the uterus and the angel says, 'O Lord, (it is) semen! O Lord, (it is now) a clot! O Lord, (it is now) a piece of flesh.' And then, if Allah wishes to complete its creation, the angel asks, 'O Lord, (will it be) a male or a female? A wretched (an evil doer) or a blessed (doer of good)? How much will his provisions be? What will his age be?' So all that is written while the creature is still in the mother's womb” (Bukari, 2009).

In the surrounding area of the embryonic kidney the genital ridge appear that will be differentiated into three different types of somites cells. These cells will be the main mass of the mature gonads (Jr., 2002). This scientific information coincides with Quranic information as it is revealed in Al-Quran,

“فَلْيَنْظُرِ الْإِنْسَانُ مِمَّ خُلِقَ خُلِقَ مِنْ مَاءٍ ذَافِقٍ يُخْرَجُ مِنْ بَيْنِ الصُّلْبِ وَالتَّرَائِبِ”

“Now let man but think from what he is created! He is created from the drop emitted proceeding from between the backbone or kidney and the ribs (Quran 86:5-7)

Scientific explanation of Quranic ayah can be seen from the books of embryology as the normal puberty and normal reproductive function is based on the establishment of this system during fetal life. The normal sexual development is dependent on the intrauterine gonadal development (Jaff's, 2004). The gonad of both sexes male or female are derived from the common somatic mesenchymal tissue develop on either side of the central dorsal, on posterior wall of thoracic (L. Thorax mean chest) and upper lumbar region at about three and half to four and half week. Thus the basic matrices of the two gonads are resulted from thoracic and upper lumbar region of mesenchyme (Johnson, 2007).

Gonadal Differentiation in the Human

(Modified from Paxton, *Endocrinology: Biological and Medical Perspectives*, W.C. Brown: Dubuque, IA, 1986.)

Conclusion

In the light of the above comparative studies, it could be concluded that the recent embryological studies prove the same information that is revealed in the Quran and explained in *hadith* fourteen hundred years ago. The information of embryology and Quran coincides at each level of organogenesis including eye, ear, muscle, bone and gonadal differentiation level.

References

- 1-Abadi, M. A. M. S. D. (1944). *Tafsir e Majidi*. Taji Company Ltd: Taji Company Ltd.
- 2-Bukari, M. b. I. a. (2009). *Sahi al Bukhari* (1st ed.).
- 3-Gilbert, S. F. (2003). *Developmental Biology* (7th ed.). Sunderland: Sinauer.
- 4-Hill, D. M. Hearing - Outer Ear Development - Embryology. Retrieved from Hearing - Outer Ear Development - Embryology (unsw.edu.au)
- 5-Jaff's, Y. a. (2004). *Reproductive Endocrinology* (5th ed.). Barnieri: Elsevier Saunder.
- 6-Johnson, M. H. (2007). *Essential Reproduction* (6th ed.). Malden: Blackwell Publishing.
- 7-Jr., R. P. (2002). *Biology of Human Reproduction*. Sandiego: University of science Book.
- 8-Muslim, I. (2009). *Mokhtaser Shai Muslaim* (1st ed.).
- 9-Persuade, M. (2003). *Before We are Born Essentials of Embryology and Birth Defect* (6th ed.). China: Saunders.
- 10-Quran
- 11-R.W. Dudek, J. D. F. *Board Review Series Embryology* (2nd ed.).
- 12-Sadler, T. W. (2003). *Langman's Medical Embryology*. Maryland: Lippincot Williams and Wilkins.

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